

Synthesis of some New 1-Benzothiazol-2'-yl-3-ethyl-4*H*-indeno[1,2-*c*]pyrazole and its 6'-Substituted Analogues

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2-Propanoylindan-1,3-dione (1) was condensed with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles (2) to give the corresponding hydrazones (3) which on treatment with refluxing acetic acid afforded the corresponding 1-(6'-substituted-benzothiazol-2'-yl)-3-ethylindeno[1,2-*c*]pyrazol-4(*H*)-4-ones (4). The Wolff-Kishner reduction of the ketones (4) gave the desired indenopyrazoles (5). The structures of these were established by elemental analysis, ir, nmr and mass spectral data.

INDENOPYRAZOLES have been reported to possess various biological properties¹. Benzothiazole nucleus plays an important role in either conferring or dramatically changing the biological activity of many molecules². These observations prompted us to undertake the synthesis of indenopyrazoles bearing benzothiazole moiety. The present paper describes the synthesis of some 1-(6'-substituted-benzothiazol-2'-yl)-3-ethyl-4*H*-indeno[1,2-*c*]pyrazoles (5) (Scheme 1). Condensation of 2-propanoylindan-1,3-dione (1)³ with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles (2a-c)⁴ in boiling ethanol gave the corresponding hydrazones (3a-c) in excellent yields. The ir spectra of these hydrazones (3)

showed characteristics bands in the region 3 150–3 100br (NH or OH), 1 665–1 660 (C=O), 1 625–1 615 (C=N) and 1 580 cm⁻¹ (NH bending). All the hydrazones gave positive Tollen's test and produced red colour with 10% aqueous NaOH solution. This behaviour is characteristic of 2-acylindan-1,3-dione hydrazones with hydrazone in the side-chain⁵.

The hydrazones (3a-c) on treatment with refluxing acetic acid yielded the corresponding pyrazolones (4a-c; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 700 cm⁻¹ C=O). A noteworthy feature of the ¹H nmr spectra of the pyrazolones is that the H-8 protons are substantially deshielded relative to other aromatic protons and appear at δ 8.15–8.45. This significant deshielding may be attributed to steric interaction with benzothiazole nucleus, since a similar assignment has been made for H-8 in 1-phenylindeno[1,2-*c*]pyrazole⁶.

The mass spectra of 4a and 4b exhibited molecular ion peaks, also the base peaks, at *m/z* 331 and 345, respectively. The important fragmentation processes are sequential losses of CO and C₂H₅CN generating respective ions at [*M*-28]⁺ and [*M*-83]⁺, and also the loss of H⁺ from molecular ion followed by loss of CO. Appearance of characteristics ions at *m/z* 107 and 121 supported the presence of benzothiazole moiety⁷. The important fragmentation processes are shown in Chart 1.

The pyrazolones on Wolff-Kishner reduction with hydrazine hydrate and ethylene glycol afforded the desired pyrazoles (5a-c). Formation of these compounds is evident from the nmr spectra, each of which showed a two-proton singlet at δ 3.82 or 3.85, assignable to C(4)-H₂ group.

Scheme 1

Chart 1

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) instrument using tetramethylsilane as internal standard.

2-Propanoylindan-1,3-dione 2-[(6'-substituted-benzothiazol-2'-yl)]hydrazone (3): A mixture of 2-propanoylindan-1,3-dione (1; 0.01 mol), 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles (2; 0.01 mol) and ethanol (60 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from DMF to yield orange-red crystals of the hydrazones (3; Table 1).

1-(6'-Substituted-benzothiazol-2'-yl)-3-ethylindeno-[1,2-c]pyrazol-4(H)-4-ones (4): The hydrazone (3; 1 g) was refluxed in acetic acid (30 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into cold water, and the resulting yellow solid was

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3-5)*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	δ (CDCl ₃)**
3a	H	246	91	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	1.45 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH ₃), 3.85 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH ₂), 7.50-8.20 (6H, m, ArH)
3b	CH ₃	278	80	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	1.45 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH ₃), 2.55 (3H, s, CH ₃ -6'), 3.35 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH ₂), 7.45-8.05 (7H, m, ArH)
3c	OCH ₃	288	82	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ S	1.45 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH ₃), 3.35 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH ₂), 4.05 (3H, s, CH ₃ O-6'), 7.45-8.05 (7H, m, ArH)
4a	H	205	84	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S	1.45 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH ₃), 2.75 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH ₂), 7.20-7.70 (5H, m, ArH), 7.85 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-7'), 7.95 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-4'), 8.45 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-8)
4b	OH	222	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S	1.40 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH ₃), 2.75 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH ₂), 7.30 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-5'), 7.40-7.80 (4H, m, ArH), 7.85 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-4'), 8.35 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-8)
4c	OCH ₃	232	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	1.45 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH ₃), 2.70 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH ₂), 3.95 (3H, s, CH ₃ O-6'), 7.15-7.70 (6H, m, ArH), 8.15 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-8)
5a	H	188	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ S	1.45 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH ₃), 2.77 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH ₂), 3.85 (2H, s, CH ₂ -4), 7.25-7.70 (6H, m, ArH), 7.85 (1H, dd, H-4'), 8.45 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-8)
5b	CH ₃	222	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ S	1.40 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH ₃), 2.52 (3H, s, CH ₃ -6'), 2.75 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH ₂), 3.85 (2H, s, CH ₂ -4), 7.35 (1H, dd, H-5'), 7.40-7.80 (4H, m, ArH), 7.86 (d, J 8 Hz, H-4'), 8.37 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-8)
5c	OCH ₃	176	72	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	1.45 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH ₃), 2.70 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH ₂), 3.85 (2H, s, CH ₂ -4), 3.97 (3H, s, CH ₃ O-6'), 7.30-7.75 (6H, m, ArH), 8.20 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-8)

* All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

** ¹H nmr spectra of 3a-c were scanned in (TFA + CDCl₃).

crystallised from EtOH - CHCl₃ to afford yellow crystals of the pyrazoles (4a - c ; Table 1).

1-(6'-Substituted-benzothiazol-2'-yl)-3-ethyl-4H-indeno[1,2-c]pyrazoles (5) : The ketone (4 ; 1 g) was heated with hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) in ethylene glycol (30 ml) first at 120° for 2 h and then at 180° for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water, and the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (5 ; Table 1).

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